

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

XAI-Optimized with ExVRes Hybrid Model for Accurate Skin Cancer Classification

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Abstract

Objectives: Classifying skin cancer is challenging because distinguishing benign from malignant lesions is difficult. This study introduces the ExVRes Hybrid model, an integrated deep learning approach designed to improve both accuracy and interpretability. **Method:** A labeled dermoscopic image dataset was constructed using sources such as the ISIC archive and split into training and testing sets for robust evaluation. All images were resized to 224×224 pixels, normalized, and converted to tensors before processing. Pretrained VGG16 and ResNet50 models extracted dual and complementary features. Key training parameters, learning rate, batch size, number of epochs, optimizer type (Adam), and dropout rates were chosen to reduce overfitting. These features were classified using a fully connected dense neural network. An Integrated Gradient-based Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) system was incorporated to identify significant features and enhance model transparency. Additionally, XAI-based guidelines were utilized for model refinement. Performance evaluation was carried out using accuracy metrics, classification reports, and confusion matrix analysis. **Findings:** ExVRes achieved 89.96% accuracy, outperforming EfficientNet-B4 (79.69%), MobileNetV2 (85.00%), and custom CNNs (86.10%). XAI improved feature relevance and reduced false negatives, enhancing clinical reliability. **Novelty:** Hybrid feature fusion and XAI-driven optimization enabled high accuracy and interpretability. ExVRes captures multiple feature representations, explains decisions, and provides a transparent, clinically viable solution for automated skin cancer diagnosis.

Keywords: Skin Cancer Classification; Explainable AI; Hybrid Deep Learning; VGG16; ResNet50; Integrated Gradients

1 Introduction

Skin cancer is a life-threatening disease; its early detection can influence and improve the prognosis of patients. Computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems and deep learning models, especially CNN-based methods are commonly leveraged to analyze clinical and dermoscopic images that classify lesions as benign or malignant. These approaches can be shown to be highly effective in the detection of melanoma, the most aggressive skin cancer type⁽¹⁾. Computer-assisted diagnostic systems based on deep learning have enabled substantial improvements in automated skin lesion classification, especially for dermoscopic images⁽²⁾. Moreover, an optimization-driven method, such as Bat Optimization for lesion boundary detection, increased segmentation efficiency by defining acceptable threshold values⁽³⁾. Recent developments in deep learning (DL), including convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and transformer-based models, have exhibited good performance. Vision Transformer (ViT)-based methods have achieved accuracy of up to 96.15% with lower false-negative rates, reinforcing their clinical applicability⁽⁴⁾. Likewise, numerous pretrained architectures have been realized (VGG16, VGG19, InceptionV3, Xception, DenseNet121, and EfficientNet), achieving a high classification accuracy, with fine-tuned versions of VGG16 reaching up to 99.3%⁽⁵⁾. R-CNN-based object detection models and hybrid architectures are also used to enhance large-scale image processing and classification⁽⁶⁾. The proposed approaches in this paper include resizing, image preprocessing, and normalization, followed by grayscale conversion and Canny edge detection for dermatology images, to prepare the data for a CNN classification model⁽⁷⁾. Furthermore, notable progress has been achieved in preprocessing and segmentation methods. Used resizes, normalization, edge detection, and morphological operations to improve feature extraction on dermoscopic datasets like ISIC-2019⁽⁸⁾. To overcome these limitations, we advocate a new hybrid deep learning approach that integrates the strengths of multiple architectures for robust feature extraction and accurate classification, helping address these challenges⁽⁹⁾. Conventional machine learning techniques, which incorporate handcrafted features such as ABCD, GLCM, and PCA with classifiers such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest, can also achieve approximately 96.25% accuracy⁽¹⁰⁾. Moreover, most successful models are based solely on small or imbalanced datasets, and, in fact, their generalization to realistic clinical settings is limited. A related limitation is the lack of interpretability. Deep learning frameworks are described as “black-box” in nature, so it is hard for clinicians to have trust in their predictions. Although some works have utilized hybrid models or optimization techniques⁽¹¹⁾. Other hybrid techniques that combine segment separation with classification, i.e., FrCN-(U-Net) systems, have also been suggested to achieve better prediction performance and facilitate clinical use⁽¹²⁾. However, traditional machine learning techniques are too dependent on handcrafted features and are not well-suited to the various and complex datasets⁽¹³⁾. Moreover, traditional machine learning techniques, which focus on manually derived features such as GLCM and ABCD rules, are not strong enough to handle large, diverse dermoscopic datasets⁽¹⁴⁾. Furthermore, public studies have shown that effective skin cancer prevention and early detection reduce skin cancer-related mortality, with large returns on investment in primary prevention⁽¹⁵⁾. Moreover, their lack of interpretability and computational complexity further limit their application in practical healthcare settings⁽¹⁶⁾. IoT has been given great importance in research on skin cancer diagnosis and classification⁽¹⁷⁾. New technologies such as IoT systems and mobile apps are revolutionizing accessibility, enabling rapid and real-time diagnosis⁽¹⁸⁾. Experimental results demonstrate improvements in accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity compared with existing methods, as well as a lower false-negative rate⁽¹⁹⁾. Furthermore, CNN was tested on a moderate-sized training dataset of 2,792 samples with suitable hyperparameters in⁽²⁰⁾. Melanoma is a highly fatal skin cancer, and early detection is crucial. Recent advances in deep learning, particularly through transfer learning and lightweight models such as MobileNetV2, have enabled the development of automated diagnosis systems. However, existing approaches often struggle to balance accuracy with computational efficiency and lack generalizability across diverse datasets. To address these challenges, we introduce a MobileNetV2-based model with an optimized classification head, achieving efficient and accurate melanoma detection (up to 85%)⁽²¹⁾. Finally, to overcome these challenges, this study offers a new XAI-optimized ExVRes Hybrid model, which:

- VGG16 (local feature extraction) and ResNet50 (global feature learning)
- Feature fusion is introduced to enhance representation.
- Incorporates Integrated Gradients-based XAI for easy interpretability.
- Improved classification accuracy and decreased false negatives.

Compared to classical data analysis methods, the proposed method offers a good balance of accuracy, robustness, and interpretability, making it well-suited for clinical settings.

2 Methodology

In contrast to traditional single-network methods (such as EfficientNet or MobileNet), the proposed model combines several architectural strengths to improve both feature extraction and representation. This hybridization improves learning ability compared to standalone models in the prior studies.

Fig 1. Basic block diagram of the proposed model

The proposed hybrid architecture analyzes preprocessed skin cancer images, employing VGG16 and ResNet50 backbones for extracting deep features. The system extracted features, which researchers combined to generate hybrid deep features. Based on these features, a fully connected classifier is developed to distinguish benign from malignant images. It uses Explainable AI with Integrated Gradients to identify features and their importance, and then performs XAI-based fine-tuning to improve model understanding and classification accuracy.

2.1 Dataset Description

The experimental evaluation uses data from the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) dataset, available at <https://www.isic-archive.com>. This public resource enables exploration of dermoscopic images and lesion categorization. The dataset consists of high-quality, expert-annotated images of benign and malignant skin lesions, providing ground-truth labels for supervised learning. A total of 2,637 dermoscopic images are used: 1,440 benign and 1,197 malignant. For fair assessment, the dataset is split into training (1,977 images, 75%) and testing (660 images, 25%) sets. The test set includes 360 benign and 300 malignant specimens, maintaining class balance. All images are resized to 224×224 pixels for input to a pretrained convolutional neural network. The dataset includes several subclasses, grouped into benign and malignant classes for binary classification, reflecting the study's main goal. Data augmentation—rotation, horizontal flipping, scaling—enhances generalization and reduces overfitting. Dropout regularization is also used to prevent overfitting. Transfer learning initializes feature-extraction networks (VGG16 and ResNet50) with pretrained weights, leveraging prior knowledge to accelerate

convergence. Models are trained using the Adam optimizer, which updates learning parameters. The proposed framework also applies XAI-based feature weighting to improve model updates, enabling greater understanding and interpretability. Table 1 shows the distribution of the dataset used in this study.

Table 1. Distribution of Skin Cancer Dataset

Class	Total Images	Training Images	Testing Images
Benign	1440	1080	360
Malignant	1197	897	300
Total	2637	1977	660

2.2 Preprocessing techniques

All input dermoscopic images are preprocessed to ensure consistency and improve model performance. Images are resized to 224×224 pixels to match the pretrained models' requirements. Pixel values are normalized, meaning they are scaled to fall within a specified range (e.g., 0 to 1) to enable faster convergence during training.

The images are then converted to tensor format to improve processing in deep learning frameworks. Furthermore, data augmentation is applied, including rotation, horizontal flipping, and scaling, to broaden the dataset's diversity and alleviate overfitting. Together, they make the model a better generalizer over new data.

2.3 Experimental Setup

- Optimizer: Adam
- Learning rate: 0.001 (training) and 0.0005 (fine-tuning)
- Epochs: 50
- Dropout: 0.3 and 0.2
- Loss function: Cross-entropy
- Validation strategy: Train-test split with controlled random seed

For reproducibility reasons:

- Used a fixed random seed

2.4 ExVRes Hybrid and XAI Optimization

The ExVRes Hybrid model integrates two strong convolutional neural networks to improve skin cancer classification accuracy. ResNet50 starts with a 7×7 convolutional layer, followed by batch normalization, ReLU activation, and max pooling. These steps extract features while maintaining important output. The core bottleneck blocks and three additional convolutional layers use batch normalization and ReLU activations via residual connections. This setup helps gradient flow and enables the learning of complex features.

At the same time, VGG16 extracts hierarchical features with sequential convolution and pooling layers. These layers capture detailed spatial and textural information. Outputs from both networks are combined—either by concatenation or by merging—to create hybrid deep features. These features combine low- and high-level image information before reaching the fully connected classifier, which separates benign from malignant cases.

This study uses Explainable AI (XAI) with Integrated Gradients to improve model interpretability. XAI assigns feature significance weights and fine-tunes them for better understanding. This approach increases classifier accuracy and clarifies which areas influence decisions for more precise predictions.

The fully connected classifier uses the merged features from VGG16 and ResNet50 to classify skin cancer. It has three linear layers: an input layer, then 512 and 128 neurons, and finally class outputs. Hidden layers use ReLU activation and dropout (0.3 and 0.2) to prevent overfitting. Training uses cross-entropy loss for multi-class classification and the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001.

In summary, this classifier is the main decision-maker in the hybrid model, turning combined features into predictions of benign or malignant skin lesions. The proposed ExVRes Hybrid model thus leverages both VGG16 and ResNet50 to enhance feature extraction and skin cancer classification.

Training Image

Benign

Testing Image

Benign

Malignant

Malignant

Fig 2. Basic block diagram of the proposed model

ResNet50 starts with a 7×7 convolutional layer, batch normalization, ReLU activation, and max pooling for early feature extraction and dimensionality reduction. Furthermore, its use of residual bottleneck blocks enables deeper learning without degradation.

Meanwhile, VGG16 extracts features layer by layer with convolution and pooling. The outputs of both networks are merged into hybrid features that inform the classifier's final binary output.

The classifier uses ReLU activation and dropout (0.3 and 0.2) to limit overfitting. It relies on cross-entropy loss and the Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.001) for model optimization.

To boost results, an XAI-based optimization is used. Feature rankings from Integrated Gradients guide improvements toward key parts of the image. This step improves accuracy and model transparency, making the model more reliable for clinical use.

2.5 Feature extraction and fusion

Feature extraction uses two pretrained convolutional neural networks: VGG16 and ResNet50, chosen for complementary learning strengths.

- Specifically, VGG16 captures detailed spatial and texture features with its deep, uniform convolutional design.
- In contrast, ResNet50's residual connections learn high-level, discriminative features while addressing vanishing gradients.

Feature maps from both networks are combined using feature fusion (concatenation) to form a unified hybrid feature vector. This allows the model to leverage both low-level (local) and high-level (global) features, improving its ability to distinguish visually similar benign and malignant lesions.

2.6 Classification

The fused hybrid feature vector trains a fully connected, dense neural network classifier. The classifier uses layers with ReLU activation functions for non-linearity and dropout layers (0.3 and 0.2) to prevent overfitting. The network is trained with a cross-entropy loss function, suitable for classification, and the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. To ensure stable convergence and optimal performance, systematically adjust hyperparameters, such as the batch size and number of epochs, based on validation set performance.

2.7 Explainable AI Integration

This study, to address the interpretability problem in deep learning models, presents explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) using the Integrated Gradients (IG) method. Integrated Gradients computes feature attribution scores by measuring the contribution of each input feature to the model's prediction. These scores are normalized and used as weights for feature importance so the model can identify and target the most critical areas of the input pictures. Using the model's importance weights, the model is fine-tuned via XAI, and its representations are fine-tuned to accentuate clinically meaningful patterns. Such a process not only enhances classification accuracy but also the transparency and trustworthiness of the model, making it suitable for practical use in real medical settings. Standard performance metrics for the proposed system are provided, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix analysis, to comprehensively evaluate the model's effectiveness.

2.8 XAI Feature Weighting

The XAI (explainable artificial intelligence) feature weighting mechanism is a key element for improving model performance. The model's attribution scores, calculated using Integrated Gradients, a method for assigning feature importance, identify which features contribute more or less to the model's predictions. These importance scores are normalized (scaled to a common range) and used as weights in the hybrid feature vector, which combines different types of feature representations. This process refines features by increasing the influence of crucial features and reducing that of less important ones. The targeted feature refinement enhances the model's accuracy and efficiency. As loss values (measures of prediction error) decrease, this suggests that the XAI mechanism has guided effective feature refinement, further improving internal representations. In turn, the model emphasizes clinically relevant patterns, thereby efficiently increasing reliability and interpretability.

2.9 Standard Training Loss Curve

A typical training loss curve displays loss values across different training epochs, indicating how the model learns from the data. In the beginning, the model shows higher loss values with mild variation, due to its learning process as it learns from the

dataset and starts classifying features. The loss values drop steadily during training, indicating a better model and performance improvement through optimization.

Fig 3. Basic block diagram of the proposed model

In the latter epochs, the loss stabilizes at a lower value, indicating that the model converges and can extract the underlying data patterns with confidence. This trend validates the training procedure and ensures that the hyperparameters appropriate for the model are selected.

2.10 XAI Fine-tuning Loss Curve

The fine-tuning stage of XAI enhances the model by integrating feature importance insights into the training process. Specifically, the model is retrained using XAI-weighted features, enabling it to prioritize the most critical attributes identified during attribution analysis. Next, optimization is performed using the Adam optimizer with a reduced learning rate of 0.0005 to ensure stable, precise parameter updates. The loss is computed by comparing predicted outputs with ground-truth labels, then backpropagating and iteratively adjusting weights. As training progresses, the fine-tuning loss curve shows a gradual decrease with slight fluctuations during the initial epochs as the model adapts to the revised feature space. Ultimately, the loss stabilizes, indicating improved convergence and learning stability.

XAI-guided fine-tuning has the potential to improve both the accuracy and interpretability of the model illustrated in Figure 4, ensuring that the final output not only performs effectively but also offers valuable insights into its predictions.

2.11 Integrated Gradients

The Integrated Gradients (IG) approach is used to study feature contributions and enrich the model's interpretability. This hybrid feature extraction uses high-dimensional matrix analysis to help the model capture intricate patterns in dermoscopic images. During training, IG calculates attribution scores to show how much each feature contributes to predictions. These findings

Fig 4. Basic block diagram of the proposed model

describe the model's decision process and highlight the most important features. Training occurs over multiple epochs, with the loss value consistently decreasing. This indicates effective learning and optimization. Early epoch variations are due to parameter tuning, and convergence stabilizes later. Integrated Gradients analysis shows that the model has learned meaningful feature representations, strengthening overall classification performance.

2.12 Proposed work

To address shortcomings in the single-model approach to skin cancer classification, this work introduces a framework, ExVRes Hybrid, that combines deep feature fusion with Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to improve precision and interpretability. The workflow comprises four sections: preprocessing, feature extraction, feature fusion and classification, and XAI-based optimization. To start with, we preprocess dermoscopic images by resizing them to 224×224 pixels, normalizing pixel intensities, and converting them to a tensor representation for deep learning models. These activities ensure consistent input and stable training. For feature extraction, two pre-trained convolutional neural networks, VGG16 and ResNet50, are used to encode complementary representations. More precisely, VGG16 extracts rich, fine-grained spatial and texture characteristics, while ResNet50 uses residual learning to capture high-level discriminative features while eliminating vanishing gradients. The outputs from both networks are then concatenated to form a hybrid feature vector, enabling the model to jointly learn local and global characteristics of skin lesions. The fused feature vector is provided to a fully connected dense neural network classifier comprising multiple layers with ReLU activations and dropout regularization. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer (learning rate = 0.001) and the cross-entropy loss function, with an appropriate batch size and number of epochs to ensure convergence and generalization. To improve model interpretability and address the black-box nature of deep learning, Integrated Gradients (IG) is incorporated as an XAI technique. IG computes feature attribution scores that quantify each input feature's contribution to the model's prediction. These attribution scores are normalized and used as feature importance weights to refine the hybrid feature space. Based on the XAI-derived insights, the model undergoes fine-tuning, with the weighted

features guiding the learning process. Doing so improves classification accuracy and interpretability, guiding the model towards clinically relevant fields through the input images. The study uses fixed random seeds, a uniform data split, and hyperparameter tuning to maintain reproducibility and perform an objective assessment. The proposed model is then evaluated against the baseline architectures, including stand-alone VGG16 and ResNet50, to confirm its efficacy. The performance of the proposed framework is finally assessed using typical metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, sensitivity, specificity, and confusion matrix analysis, which assess general classification capabilities.

2.13 Novelty of Method

The innovation in this work is in:

- Hybrid Feature Fusion: Utilizes the best features of VGG16 and ResNet50
- XAI-Guided Optimization: Integrated Gradients used for feature weighting
- Enhanced Interpretability: Transparent decision making
- Balanced Performance: High accuracy with reduced false negatives

3 Results and Discussion

The proposed ExVRes Hybrid model achieves 89.96% accuracy in skin cancer classification, outperforming widely used architectures such as EfficientNet-B4 (79.69%) [Harahap et al., 2024], MobileNetV2 (85.00%) [Indraswari et al., 2022], customized CNNs (86.10%) [Anitha et al., 2022], and EfficientNet-B0 (88.00%) [Georges et al., 2025]. These results align with recent findings that hybrid and ensemble-based deep learning models outperform single-architecture approaches in medical image analysis by leveraging complementary feature representations. The improved performance of ExVRes can be attributed to its feature-level fusion of VGG16 and ResNet50, enabling the extraction of both low-level texture and high-level semantic features, which are critical for accurate lesion differentiation. Additionally, the integration of Integrated Gradients enhances interpretability and guides the model toward clinically relevant regions, supporting recent research emphasizing the role of explainable AI in improving both transparency and model performance. However, consistent with prior studies, the increased accuracy comes at the cost of higher computational complexity and potential overfitting, particularly in limited datasets, making lightweight models like MobileNetV2 more suitable for real-time or resource-constrained environments. Overall, the findings reinforce the idea that even modest accuracy gains can have significant clinical implications, particularly by reducing false-negative diagnoses in conditions such as melanoma.

3.1 Evaluation Metrics and Performance Analysis

The model is evaluated on standard performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix). The trained model is evaluated on the test dataset, making predictions, and class labels are assigned based on the maximum probability scores. The classification report summarizes the model's performance across both benign and malignant classes.

3.2 Confusion Matrix Analysis

These results show that the model achieves high true-positive and true-negative rates. This demonstrates its effectiveness in distinguishing benign from malignant lesions. False negatives (malignant cases misclassified as benign) are rare, an important factor in medical diagnosis since missed cancer cases have significant clinical consequences. The model performs consistently across both classes and minimizes misclassification errors. Specifically, the XAI-based optimization process enhances performance by selecting and prioritizing diagnostically relevant features during model training, thereby reducing classification confusion.

Figure 5. The confusion matrix provides further insight into classification performance. 254 of these samples are correctly classified as benign, but 30 are misclassified as malignant out of 284 benign samples. Out of 221 diagnosed malignant samples, 202 are classified as true positive and 19 are classified as benign.

3.3 Comparative Analysis

The study shows that the hybrid framework is a high-performance, collaborative model that leverages multi-model feature extraction and clear XAI-based refinement.

As shown in Table 2, the ExVRes Hybrid model with XAI-based optimization achieved the highest accuracy of 89.96%, outperforming EfficientNet-B4, MobileNetV2, custom models, and EfficientNet-B0.

Fig 5. Basic block diagram of the proposed model

Table 2. Accuracy Comparison of Existing Models

Model	Accuracy (%)
EfficientNet-B4	79.69
MobileNetV2	85.00
Customized CNN	86.10
EfficientNet-B0	88.00
Proposed ExVRes Hybrid Model	89.96

A graph illustrates the accuracy percentages of different deep learning methods tested in the investigation. This bar plot compares EfficientNet, MobileNetV2, and other methods. The proposed Hybrid ExVRes model, which integrates elements from VGG16 and ResNet50, has the highest accuracy.

3.4 Key Contributions of the Proposed Model

This work introduces a Hybrid architecture combining VGG16 and ResNet50 to capture complementary features. It enhances feature learning for better discrimination of visually similar skin lesions and integrates Gradients with XAI for interpretability and transparency. There is a reduction in false negatives, improving the reliability of cancer detection, and the model maintains stable performance on test data.

Fig 6. Basic block diagram of the proposed model

3.5 Discussion

The results show that while conventional architectures such as EfficientNet and MobileNet perform well, they cannot fully exploit hybrid feature representations, thereby limiting their ability to capture complex data patterns. The proposed ExVRes model addresses this by using a hybrid design that enables richer feature diversity and improved learning. The integration of Explainable AI (XAI) increases interpretability, enabling clinicians to better understand model decisions than with black-box models, thereby strengthening its value in clinical decision support. ExVRes combines high classification accuracy with enhanced reliability, transparency, and robustness required for effective use in medical environments.

The ExVRes Hybrid model demonstrates strong performance in skin cancer classification, achieving 89.96% accuracy and outperforming recent deep learning approaches such as EfficientNet-B4 (79.69%) [Harahap et al., 2024], MobileNetV2 (85.00%) [Indraswari et al., 2022], customized CNNs (86.10%) [Anitha et al., 2022], and EfficientNet-B0 (88.00%) [Georges et al., 2025]. Although the improvements appear incremental (1.96%–10.27%), they are clinically meaningful, particularly in reducing false-negative rates in melanoma detection, where early diagnosis is critical. The performance gain is mainly attributed to hybrid feature-level fusion of VGG16 and ResNet50, which enables the extraction of both fine-texture and deep-semantic features for better lesion discrimination. Additionally, the integration of Integrated Gradients improves interpretability and helps focus learning on clinically relevant regions, aligning with recent trends where explainable AI enhances both transparency and performance. Overall, the findings support existing literature that hybrid architectures improve medical image classification, while also highlighting a key trade-off between accuracy, interpretability, and efficiency.

4 Conclusion

This research reports an XAI-optimized ExVRes Hybrid model for precise and interpretable skin cancer classification. Building on the strengths of VGG16 and ResNet50, the model captures local and global feature representations from dermoscopic images. The performance of our proposed model was 89.96% on the ISIC dataset, which is better than several existing state-of-the-art models. The integration of Integrated Gradients also benefits model interpretability by discovering significant features that contribute to classification decisions.

First, the main merits of this work were as follows:

- XAI-driven feature optimization boosts interpretability.
- Superior classifier performance minimizes false negatives.
- Robust predictions deliver strong clinical relevance.

Therefore, the proposed framework ensures a trustworthy, interpretable predictive mechanism for automated skin cancer diagnosis, helping clinicians detect skin cancer early and make prompt decisions.

In future research, attention will be given to:

- Generalizing the model to multi-class skin lesion classification.
- Introducing state-of-the-art XAI methods, including Grad-CAM and SHAP.
- Building lightweight architectures targeted at mobile and real-time healthcare applications.
- Broadening data to extend generalization for various populations.

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About authors: S. Vadivel Murugan is a Research Scholar; Dr. J. G. R. Sathiaselan is an Associate Professor who also serves as Research Supervisor, Vice Principal and Head.

References

- 1) Malika DKS, Rahaman SS, Veramallu B. Skin cancer detection using deep learning techniques. *International Journal of Research Publication and Review*. 2025 Mar;6:7590–7592. Available from: <https://www.ijrpr.com>.
- 2) Dessai SS, Polawar S, Patro SR, Cheralu S, Sowmya N. Skin cancer detection using deep learning. *International Journal of Science Engineering and Technology*. 2025;p. 1–5. Available from: https://www.ijset.in/wp-content/uploads/IJSET_V13_issue3_330.pdf.
- 3) Abed MSA, Akbas A. An approach in melanoma skin cancer segmentation with bat optimization algorithm. *International Journal of Imaging Systems and Technology*. 2024 May. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ima.23119>.
- 4) Himel GMS, Islam MM, Al-Aff KA, Karim SI, Sikder MKU. Skin cancer segmentation and classification using vision transformer for dermatoscopy-based analysis. *International Journal of Biomedical Imaging*. 2024 Feb. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/3022192>.
- 5) Eliwa EHI. Enhancing skin cancer diagnosis through fine-tuning of pretrained models: A two-phase transfer learning approach. *International Journal of Breast Cancer*. 2025 Jan. <https://doi.org/10.1155/ijbc/4362941>.
- 6) Kar US, Manjula V, Kuljarni MJ, Yeramati H, Nazneen H, Manasa M, et al. Advanced deep learning method using IoT and CNN for early diagnosis of skin cancer. *International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering Hub*. 2025 Jul. <https://doi.org/10.47392/IRJAEH.2025.0477>.
- 7) Vaishnavi B, Nithya P, Haseena S, Sultana SS. Assessing skin cancer awareness: A survey on detection methods. *Proceedings of ICCPCI*. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1051/itmconf/2025740100>.
- 8) Afrifa S, Varadarajan V, Appiahene P, Zhang T, Gyamfi D, Gyening RMO. Deep neural networks for skin cancer classification: Analysis of melanoma data. *Journal of Advanced Information Technology*. 2025 Jan;16(1):1–11. <https://doi.org/10.12720/jait.16.1.1-11>.
- 9) Georges GO, Evina HK, Aminou H, Medzo CA. A method for detecting skin cancer disease based on deep learning. *Journal of Computer and Communications*. 2025 Mar;13:138–155. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jcc.2025.133010>.
- 10) Dhore P, Waghmare T, Balwadkar S, Vetal S. Optimised skin cancer detection using random forest and support vector machine. *Journal of Emerging Trends and Novel Research*. 2025 Mar. Available from: <https://www.jetnr.org>.
- 11) Alshdaifat N, Mohammad SI, Al-Daoud KI, Abuowaida S, Vasudevan A, Amoush MSA, et al. Triple-stream transformer architecture for multi-class skin cancer classification. *Journal of Posthumanism*. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.63332/joph.v5i3.853>.
- 12) Thapar P, Rakhra M, Prashar D, Msrice L, Khan AA, Kadry S. Skin cancer segmentation and classification using hybrid FrCN-(U-Net). *PLoS One*. 2025 Jun. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0322659>.
- 13) Monika MK, Vignesh NA, Kumari CU, Kumar MNVSS, Lydia EL. Skin cancer detection and classification using machine learning. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2020 Jul. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.07.366>.
- 14) Mali SU, Gupta VJ, Jain RC, Jagtap SM, Gupta MP. Advanced skin cancer detection using machine learning. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science Communication and Technology*. 2025 May. Available from: <https://www.ijarsct.co.in>.
- 15) Garbe C, Forsea AM, Amaral T, Arenberger P, Autier P, Berwick M, et al. Skin cancer prevention and early detection. *European Journal of Cancer*. 2024 Apr. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2024.114074>.
- 16) Zareen SS, Hossain MS, Wang J, Kang Y. Recent innovations in machine learning for skin cancer analysis. *Precision Medicine Sciences*. 2025 Jan. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prm2.12156>.
- 17) Mary XA, Winifred P, Evangeline CS, Kumaravelu VB, Karthik C, Chowdhury S. Smartphone-based skin lesion detection using deep learning algorithms. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applied Engineering*. 2022. Available from: <https://www.ijisae.org>.
- 18) Supreetha S, Naik R. Skin cancer classification and detection. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*. 2024 Oct. Available from: <https://www.ijrar.org>.
- 19) Harahap M, Husein AM, Kwok SC, Wizley V, Leonardi J, Ong DK. Skin cancer classification using EfficientNet architecture. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*. 2024 Feb. <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v13i4.7159>.
- 20) Tchema RB, Polycarpou AC, Nestoros M. Skin cancer classification using machine learning. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. 2025 Jan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-025-20595-7>.
- 21) Indraswari R, Rokhana R, Herulambang W. Melanoma image classification based on MobileNetV2 network. *Procedia Computer Science, Sixth Information Systems International Conference*. 2022;p. 198–207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.132>.